

A LITERATURE REVIEW ON ACTION OF *METHIKA CHURNA* ON *BEEJA*, *BEEJABHAGA* AND *BEEJABHAGAVAYAVA DUSHTI* IN *AARTAVAKSHAYA*

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ABSTRACT

In Modern science genetics may appear a recent developing branch, but thousands of years ago in Ayurved Samhitas The Concept of genetics was written in brief by *Acharyas*. *Rutu*, *Kshetra*, *Ambu* and *beej* are the main four factors for normal conception.^[1] Vitiation in these can cause deformity in the progeny. So Ayurveda aims to correct these factors for fertility management. Ayurvedic scholars resembles *Beeja* with whole gamete –Sperm in male and Ovum in female, *Beejabhaga* with Chromosomes, *Beejabhagavayava* is the most fundamental entity which can be compared with genes and hormonal micro environment.^[2] Various types of *Streebeeja Dushti* are mentioned in *Yonivyapat* and *Ashta aartava dushti*^[3] Here we are presenting Literature review of action of *Methika Churna* on *Aartavakshaya* which is different from *Vataj Aartava dushti* and *Kshinarta*^[4] In Modern medicine it can be correlated with

oligomenorrhea. Oligomenorrhea means the menstrual periods occur at interval of greater than 35 days. Hormonal imbalance is the main cause explained in allopathy and the preferred treatment is Combined Oral Contraceptive pills and Hormone Replacement Therapy.^[5] Long term use of Hormonal therapy has many side effects. To Avoid this problem and to cure the root cause of *Beejdushti* in *Artavakshaya* this study is beneficial. In this study we have highlighted *Hetu*, *Lakshana*, *Samprapti*, *Chikitsa* of *Artavakshaya*. Relevance of *Beej*, *Beejabhaga* and *Beejabhagavayava* in *Artavakshaya* and action of *methika churna* to overcome *beejdushti*.

Beeja- Gamete integrity- family tendency for *Aartavakshaya*. *Beejabhaga*- chromosomal abnormality causing *aartavkshaya*.

Beejabhagavayava - Organ specific genetic mutations or polymorphisms causing altered enzyme activity Acharya Sushruta's this concept perfectly matches the genetic basis of *aartavakshaya* where defects at different genetic levels lead to ovarian Dysfunction can lead to infertility.

According to Modern aspect *Aartavakshaya* can be compared with oligomenorrhea.

Beejadushti - includes compromised quality and maturation of oocyte. This can affect their reproductive potential and compromise proper maturation. A significant proportion of oocytes may fail to complete their meiotic division, a process called maturation arrest. Many women with oligomenorrhea do not release a mature ovum with each cycle. The gamete release is often unpredictable, irregular or may not happen at all.

Beejabhaga Dushti: It includes oligomenorrhea caused due to chromosomal abnormalities like Turner's syndrome(45,X), Trisomy X (47,XXX), mosaicism that involves a mixture of cell lines such as 45,X/46, XX or 45, X/46,XY.^[13]

Beejabhagavayava Dushti – Unlike single gene disorders the genetic contribution to oligomenorrhea involve multiple gene acting alongside environmental factors.

Fragile X premutation gene – women who are premutation carriers of this gene (61-200CGG repeats) are at increased risk of Primary ovarian insufficiency subsequently oligomenorrhea. Increased mRNA from the premutation leads to ovarian dysfunction.

Kallmann Syndrome- rare genetic disorder affecting Hypothalamic –pituitary regulation leading to GnRH deficiency, irregular menstrual cycles and oligomenorrhea.

Prader–Wili syndrome –involving hypogonadism that can cause incomplete puberty and oligomenorrhea.^[14]

Action of *Methika Churna* on *Beeja Dushti* in *Aartavakshaya* i.e. Oligomenorrhea. *Methika* is known to enhance the quality and quantity of *Aartava*, supporting ovulation in women.

By nourishing *shukra dhatu*, *methika* boosts reproductive vitality, aiding in conception.

Tikta and *ushna guna* help in reducing *kapha* and *vata* imbalances in the reproductive organs, promoting regular menstrual cycles and reducing cyst formation in PCOS. It nourishes endometrial lining, facilitating embryo implantation.

Active principles of *methika* are Diosgenin, Trigonelline, Galactomannan, Saponins and alkaloids.

Diosgenin: A steroidal saponin that exhibits estrogenic activity, supporting hormonal imbalance.

Studies Have shown that Diosgenin can improve the ovarian reserve, leading to higher number of primary follicles and serum AMH levels. It stimulates basic functions like proliferation and hormone release.

Trigonelline- an alkaloid with neuroprotective and anti-inflammatory properties, contributing to overall reproductive health. It activates NRF2 factor that regulates antioxidant responses. It leads to upregulation of epidermal growth factor gene(EGF). EGF activates its receptor which increases phosphorylation of AKT. Activated AKT phosphorylates FOXO3A causing its relocalization. This effect removes its inhibitory effect and allowing the primordial follicles to activate and start growing.

4-Hydroxyisoleucine- an amino acid that enhances insulin sensitivity, benefiting reproductive function by regulating metabolic health.^[15]

CONCLUSION

In summary, *Methika* is beneficial for the gynecological disorders but as for the properties of *methika* and its active constituents, it is suggested that their potential roles are evaluated for their effects in the treatment of *Artavakshaya* and its role on *Beeja*, *Beejabhaga* and *beejabhagavayava*. The specific aspects delineated in Ayurvedic classics still provides ample opportunity to carryon further research to understand therapeutic role of *Methika*.

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